

Thermomechanical and Fatigue Testing of Woven and Prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) using a unique combustion materials test facility

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SUMMARY

Two Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs), woven Melt-Infiltrated (MI) Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC and prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, were studied for their fatigue behavior in a combustion environment using a unique burner rig facility. S-N data and micrographic analysis determined the prepreg MI CMC possess better mechanical properties as well as greater long-term potential in an oxidative service environment.

Keywords: Combustion, burner rig, fatigue, oxidation, Hi-Nicalon Type S, SiC matrix, BN interphase, CMC, Melt-Infiltration (MI), Prepreg MI and Slurry cast MI

INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide (SiC) fibers reinforced in silicon carbide matrix composites with boron nitride (BN) interphase (SiC/BN/SiC) CMCs are among the prominent class of materials which have potential to replace nickel-based alloys for gas turbine engine applications [1]. In the harsh combustion environment of a gas turbine engine, however, oxidation can deteriorate the structural integrity as well as load bearing capability of the SiC/BN/SiC CMC components, reducing their design margin over time. A few studies have been conducted to investigate this deleterious phenomenon [2,3,4], many of which have been carried out using less realistic engine environments. Therefore, a burner rig, which will be referred to as AFIT/AFRL burner rig, was developed that provides a better simulation to a realistic service environment. In addition, two types of SiC/BN/SiC CMCs, namely woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC and prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, were characterized under the combined mechanical fatigue and combustion environment using the burner rig to simulate the combustion condition of hot-section components of gas turbine engines.

EXPERIMENTS

AFIT/AFRL Burner Rig

The AFIT/AFRL burner rig, depicted in Figure 1, is a one-of-a-kind mechanical test facility that provides a unique capability of characterizing a coupon-size specimen under various simulated combustion and mechanical loading conditions of gas turbine engine components. The facility is unique for its integration of a true combustion

environment to a mechanical test capability. An atmospheric pressure burner rig system mixes fuel and oxidizers to generate high temperature, high speed combustion flame that impinges on the specimen. The angle of impingement can be varied to simulate an angled impingement. The specimen under the flame impingement simultaneously undergoes a controlled mechanical loading condition by an MTS servo-hydraulic material testing system. The burner rig system produces hot combustion gas which travel downstream at a sub-Mach speed, providing usefulness to simulate a turbine environment of advanced gas turbine engines. Thermal cycling is facilitated by a programmable mechanical actuation of the flame in and out of engagement with the specimen. The mechanical loading can be applied either in a sustained manner to study a creep scenario or a cyclic way to investigate fatigue behavior.

The current configuration of this facility was rendered to investigate the fatigue behaviors of two CMCs in a realistic combustion condition. For turbine airfoils, it was of particular interest to investigate this in the presence of a thermal gradient, which exists in the service environment. Hence, the AFIT/AFRL burner rig was configured such that a non-symmetric thermal field was rendered on the test specimen by imposing the combustion condition on one side of the specimen only, while the other side was allowed to undergo natural convection with the ambient laboratory air. The stress induced by temperature gradients across the specimen dimensions either add to or subtract from the applied peak stress such that a local stress state could be higher (or lower) than the applied peak stress. Specific objectives of this study were to compare fatigue behavior of the woven and prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC CMCs in a prescribed combustion environment.

Figure 1: AFIT/AFRL Burner Rig

Materials and Specimens

Both the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC CMC and the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC were provided by GE Aviation. The fibers were Hi-Nicalon Type S, which have the density of 3.05 g/cm^3 and are near-stoichiometric SiC fibers having the chemical composition: 69 weight % (wt %) of silicon (Si), 31 wt % of carbon (C) and 0.2 wt % of oxygen (O) [5]. For the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, the fiber tows, each containing approximately 500 individual fibers, were woven in a five harness satin weave (5HS) into a cloth, which is warp-aligned with the other 7 cloths in $0^\circ/90^\circ$ pattern before the preform was slurry casted in SiC and then followed by Si melt-infiltration (MI) process for matrix

densification. The fiber volume fraction was 35.7% [6], and the matrix porosity was approximately 8%, which was determined from the area fraction analysis of the voids or pores from optical images using the built-in function of the Photoshop.

The prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC has lower porosity in the matrix by virtue of the enhanced processing technique known as the prepreg MI processing developed by General Electric Global Research Center (GEGRC) [7]. Each individual Hi-Nic-S fiber is coated with a double-layer of BN interphase and then with a thin protective Si₃N₄ layer by the CVD process. Fiber tow is then impregnated by being run through matrix slurry. Using the subsequent wet drum winding process, unidirectional tapes are formed. Eight of the tapes are laid up and laminated in [0/90/90/0]_s to shape into preforms before the MI processing is applied [7,8]. Its low porosity level, i.e. < 1 vol %, is attributed to the prepreg melt-infiltration process that facilitated the uniform coating.

In this study, the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC is compared with the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, i.e. comparison of the two different processing techniques; slurry cast and prepreg methods. The two materials share the same fiber type, i.e. Hi-Nicalon Type-S. There also exists close similarities in the matrix and interphase, i.e. silicon-doped BN in the interphase and SiC melt-infiltrated with Si constituting the MI matrix. However, the two CMCs have distinct differences in the volume fraction of each constituent, the matrix porosity level, and the chemical composition and the volume of CVI matrix; all of which are results of the different methods of processing. The material data for the two CMCs are summarized in Table 1.

The specimens tested in this study were dog-bone shaped with the dimensions shown in Table 1. With similar dimensions and temperature fields on both the woven and prepreg MI specimens, the thermal gradient stresses are considered similar, allowing the comparison without an in-depth consideration of the difference in the effects of thermal gradients.

Table 1: Material Data for woven and prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC CMCs [6,7]

	Fiber vol %	Matrix porosity, %	Pattern	Layup	Plies	Dimensions* (mm)		
						Width	Thickness	Length
Woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC	35.7	~8	5HS	Warp-aligned	8	10.16 ± 0.04	2.31 ± 0.03	150.4
Prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC	20~25	< 1	Prepreg Tape	[0/90/90/0] _s	8	10.11 ± 0.02	2.00 ± 0.01	150.4

* Width and Thickness were measured in the reduced section

AFIT/AFRL Burner Rig Testing

Prior to the actual testing, the AFIT/AFRL burner rig was calibrated for the parameters as specified in Table 2. The combustion condition chosen for this study was to simulate an application environment for hot section components in modern gas turbine engine such as airfoils. Readers may refer to Ref [9] for details of calibration. Surface temperature was measured using the FLIR ThermoCAM P640 infrared (IR) thermal imaging system. Infrared images were taken periodically to monitor the temperature field during the test. With the single-sided heating of the current burner rig configuration, each test specimen experienced thermal gradients, which involved a drop

in surface temperature as much as 450°C across the specimen thickness. The surface temperature on the back of the heated zone was approximately 900 ± 50°C. Gas composition in the combustion was assumed as predicted by a computer code, i.e. Chemical Equilibrium with Applications (CEA) [10] based on the calibration described in Ref [9]. The amounts of combustion reactants such as propane and oxygen were calibrated and adjusted such that the amount of moisture in the product was approximately 50 vol % in the invicid core of the premixed flame and approximately 30 vol % in the outer ring of the flame core, where the ambient air is entrained to dilute the flame contents.

Table 2: Test Parameters

Test Parameter	Condition	Calibration Method(s)
Surface Temperature	~1235°C	Furnace, R-type TC & IR
Gas Temperature	< 1800°C	R-type TC
Gas Velocity	~ Mach 0.5	XS-4 High Speed Camera
Equivalence Ratio	~ 0.9	HVOF TM Flow Controller
Gas Composition	$H_2O, O_2, CO_2, CO, NO_x$	Testo XL 350 Gas Analyzer
Mechanical Loading	Fatigue (1 Hz & R = 0.05)	MTS
Test Duration	Up to 25 hours	N/A

Under the combustion environment, characterized by the parameters in Table 2, test specimens of both the woven and the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC CMCs were fatigued at different peak stress, while the stress ratio (R) and cyclic frequency remained constant throughout the testing phase at stress ratio, R = 0.05 and frequency of 1 Hz. The test data including the applied peak stress, the number of cycles at failure and the location of fracture were recorded from each fatigue test. After these tests, detailed microscopic analysis using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was carried out. The entire fracture cross-section was thoroughly scanned under SEM for detailed fractography and documentation of oxidative features.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Room Temperature Tensile Properties

The proportional limit (PL) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) under the monotonic tensile loading condition for both CMC systems were obtained to develop the basic material information. The PL was determined using a 0.00005 mm/mm offset strain criterion from the initial linear part of stress-strain curve. These material properties were available from the manufacturer. The average PLs for the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC and prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC were 121 and 197 MPa, respectively while their UTS were 334 and 340 MPa, respectively. The strains corresponding to the UTSs were 0.54 % and 0.71 %, respectively. In addition, the modulus of elasticity (E) was 195 GPa for the woven MI CMC and 264 GPa for the prepreg MI CMC. Further, the woven MI CMC and prepreg MI CMC had the fiber volume fraction of 35.7 vol % and 20~25 vol %, respectively.

S-N Data Comparison

The applied peak stress from each fatigue test was plotted against the corresponding number of cycles at failure for each material to develop the S-N curves as shown in

Figure 2. The fatigue life increased with decreasing peak stress, indicating the rate of damage development is related to the applied peak stress. The test runout was attained at the peak stress of 105 MPa for the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, as compared to the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC with the runout strength significantly lower at 70 MPa. The runout is defined in this study when the specimen did not fail within 90,000 cycles (or 25 hours). The dense matrix along with low porosity stemming from the prepreg MI process is believed to be accountable for the increased fatigue strength for prepreg MI CMC. In Figure 2, the S-N curve for the prepreg MI CMC has smaller slope than the woven MI CMCs. The amount of knockdown in fatigue at runout relative to the room temperature UTS was greater for the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC. The runout stresses of the prepreg MI and the woven MI CMCs, 105 MPa and 70 MPa, were quite similar when viewed in relation to the PLs, i.e. 55 % and 58 % of their respective room temperature PLs.

Figure 2: S-N data of the prepreg MI and the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC

Residual strength comparisons

The specimens of the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC and the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC that survived the fatigue test without fracture were subsequently tested for the residual strength at room temperature. The stress-strain data from the monotonic tension testing of the runout specimens are plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Stress-strain responses of two runout samples of different types

In comparing the retained strength properties to those of as-processed, the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC fatigue at the peak stress of 105 MPa retained 78% of its UTS at room temperature, while the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC retained less than 50% of its virgin strength. The two runout specimens underwent the peak stress level similar in terms of the fractions of their respective PLs. Thus, the higher stress and strain retained by the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC suggests that the prepreg MI CMC has a higher potential than the woven MI CMCs for structural applications subjected to a fatigue loading in the combustion environment.

Micrographic comparison: Fracture surfaces

The fracture surfaces of specimens from both CMC systems, subjected to the applied peak stress of 125 ± 2 MPa, are compared in Table 3 to determine the extent of oxidation. The 125 MPa is equal to 66% of the PL for the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, but is 103% of the PL for the woven Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC. From each fracture surface, micrographic features showing oxidation, shown in Figure 4, were identified, and the area rich with these features as well as a relatively planar fracture with no or less fiber pullout is termed as “oxidized” region and is denoted on the figure by “Ox”. The rest of the fracture surface showing fiber pullout with no oxidative features is denoted as “Non-embrittled”. This region is from the material failure due to the inability of the remaining presumably intact fibers to sustain the applied load.

Figure 4: (A) Degraded Interphases by hardening through oxidation on woven MI CMC and (B) the silica overlayer on prepreg MI CMC

Table 3: Fracture surfaces of the specimens fatigued at the peak stress of 125 MPa

Peak Stress (MPa)	CMC Type	Fracture Surface	Cycles-to-failure
125 ± 2	Woven MI Hi-Nic-S /BN/SiC		8329
	prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S /BN/SiC		758

1 mm

From Table 3, it can be seen that the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC survived much higher number of cycles while showing less oxidized area than the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC. Considering that the applied peak stress of 125 ± 2 MPa was a higher stress level for the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC with the PL of 121 MPa than for the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC with the PL of 197 MPa, the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC can be expected to have undergone a greater degree of matrix cracking that would translate to a larger oxidized area and generally reduced number of cycles-to-failure, if the conditions were similar including the test duration. However, the observation was that the prepreg MI CMC exhibited a large oxidized area for a relatively short time of testing. Assuming the difference in the fatigue life was not inherited from the scatter in their strength properties, this seemingly inexplicable outcome could be attributed to a multiple of causes, all of which trace back to the fundamental difference that exists between the two systems; they are different systems built on different manufacturing concepts that demonstrate different mechanical behaviors. This was evident from the as-received woven MI CMC that exhibited significantly longer pullout than the prepreg MI CMC under room temperature monotonic tension. The woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC is constructed with the bundled fiber tows enclosing hundreds of densely populated fibers, which limits the wettability around the individual fibers during melt-infiltration. This results in relatively low matrix density and high void concentration, unlike the prepreg MI CMC, and undermines the overall material's capability to carry load. The ranges of the parameters that could affect the damage including crack nucleation and propagation are likely different for the two material systems.

For the prepreg MI CMC with low fiber volume fraction, the surface area over which the load transfer occurs between the fibers and matrix is less than in the woven MI CMC with high fiber volume fraction. As a result, relatively higher shear stress would be acting upon any given fiber in the prepreg MI CMC. A microscopic observation that may relate to this is the relatively short fiber pullout exhibited throughout the non-embrittled area. The sliding distance would decrease with the increased shear stress that needs to be overcome for debonding to occur. With this, the probability of fiber fracture as well as the energy that is released upon failure of a load carrying fiber increases. The higher energy released from the fracture of each bridging fiber increases the rate of crack propagation. The oxidation would follow the advancing crack tip under cyclic load. This is one possible scenario that provides an explanation for the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC showing a large oxidized area over relatively short test duration.

Fiber pullout behaviors

Figure 5 depicts the fiber pullout in the non-embrittled region of the woven MI and the prepreg MI CMCs that fractured under fatigue. It is evident from the comparison of the fiber pullout lengths that the woven MI has much longer pullout. The woven MI and the prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC specimens depicted in the figure were subjected to 80 MPa and 125 MPa during the fatigue test, respectively. The pullout length observed from the woven MI CMC specimen that underwent 127 MPa was too long to be captured in the shown magnification. Instead, the specimen tested at 80 MPa with considerably shorter pullout was shown to demonstrate the difference in the pullout length between the two CMCs. In addition, the fracture surface of the prepreg MI CMC can be multi-faceted, as shown in Figure 5B. The uniform coating in the prepreg MI processing resulted in the finely dispersed fibers that were distributed evenly throughout the area at the expense of a relatively low fiber volume fraction. The difference in the

distribution and volume fraction of the fiber would affect the failure mode, as evident from the different fractographic appearances shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Fiber pullout of the two CMCs; (A) long fiber pullout typical of the woven MI CMC, (B) short pullout typical of the prepreg MI CMC

It was shown that the fiber pullout length of the woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC was inversely related to the number of fatigue cycles or the time exposed to the combustion [9]. The sample under lower applied stress level that survived a larger number of cycles showed significantly shorter fiber pullout. The prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, however, did not show such trend. In fact, the pullout length did not vary with either the applied stress or the number of cycles.

Micrographic comparison: Residual fracture surfaces

The fractographic investigation of the fracture surfaces obtained from the residual strength tests of a runout prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC revealed only a trace of oxidation was observed along the edges and corners, where cracks are prone to nucleate and grow from. This type of oxidation likely occurs behind the crack tip which develops under fatigue. The fracture of the runout prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC specimen fatigue-loaded to the peak stress of 105 MPa occurred at a cross-section 25 mm distant from the geometric center, at which the surface temperature was estimated to be $1025 \pm 25^\circ\text{C}$ on the front (and $845 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ on the back). This observation, along with the oxidative micrographic features found on the fracture surface, suggests that the degradation at this cross-section could have driven by the intermediate temperature phenomenon known as embrittlement [2,4]. From a different perspective, however, the cross-section of the failure is approximately where the highest thermally induced tensile stress is experienced on the plies near the unheated surface. More in-depth discussion will be reported in a future publication. There were no signs of “picture-frame” oxidation [4] on this fracture surface. The regions on this surface microscopically determined to contain the oxidative features include side edges and corners. Deeper permeation of oxidation was observed on select 90° plies, leading to the speculation that the fracture in the weaker 90° plies may have served as ingress route for the load-carrying fibers on the adjacent 0° plies.

The woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC that survived the test with the peak stress of 70 MPa fractured under the subsequent residual strength test at 25 mm from the geometric center, where the temperature during test was approximately $1185 \pm 35^\circ\text{C}$ on the front surface (and $910 \pm 25^\circ\text{C}$ on the back). The failure outside the heated gauge length,

together with the micrographic features indicating oxidation as illustrated in Table 4 suggests that the failure may have been driven by either or both the intermediate temperature embrittlement or the thermal gradient stress, as discussed above. The fracture surface showed oxidation extending from the left edge which appears to have taken place behind the cracks emanating from the rear left corner. The extent of oxidation on this surface is significantly larger than on the fracture surface of the runout prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC. The observation that less oxidation observed from the runout prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC that underwent higher peak stress than the runout woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC showing larger oxidized area suggests that the prepreg MI CMC with dense matrix was less prone to oxidation.

Table 4: Fracture surfaces from residual strength tests

Peak Stress (MPa)	CMC Type	Residual Fracture Surface	Residual Strength (MPa)
105	prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC		263
70	Woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC		186

CONCLUSION:

Two CMCs, woven MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC and prepreg MI Hi-Nic-S/BN/SiC, were characterized for their fatigue behaviors in a combustion environment using the AFIT/AFRL burner rig facility. From their S-N behaviors, the prepreg MI CMC showed the runout stress of 105 MPa, as compared to 70 MPa of the woven MI CMC. The two runout stresses were quite similar when compared in terms of their respective PLs, 55 % and 58 % of their respective room temperature PLs. The retained strength and strain of the runout specimen of the prepreg MI CMC were greater than those of the runout woven MI CMC.

The higher strength and strain retained by the runout specimen of the prepreg MI CMC could be due to its dense matrix from the uniform coating facilitated by the prepreg MI processing. It was speculated that the two different material systems may be governed by different ranges of the parameters that determine the damage evolution. This view was supported in part by different appearances in the fracture surfaces of the two CMCs. Fiber pullout of the prepreg MI CMC was considerably short and did not appear to vary with the applied stress or fatigue life, unlike the woven MI CMC that exhibited significantly longer fiber pullout that decreased with the number of fatigue cycles.

The traces of oxidation were observed on retention strength fracture surface along the edges on fracture surfaces, suggesting that the oxidation occurred in the wake of the advancing crack tip under fatigue. The fracture location of 25 mm from the specimen center for two runout specimens of both CMC types led to the speculation that the intermediate temperature embrittlement and/or the thermal gradient stress, which peaks approximately at this location, could be the cause of the degradation that led to failure.

This suggests that, in airfoil applications, thermal stress and intermediate temperature embrittlement could be just as much damaging factors in reducing the fatigue life of the CMC as are the exposure to the harsh combustion environment and mechanical loading.

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